

MEMORANDUM

To The Clerk to the Committee, Committee on Constitutional, Legal & Parliamentary Affairs, Office of Parliament, Osu-Accra

From Concerned Ghanaian Citizens in the Diaspora

Subject Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

Date September 27, 2021

We appreciated the opportunity provided by the Committee to submit a memorandum as you review the proposed *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021*.

We represent a group of concerned Ghanaian citizens studying and teaching at various universities abroad, and we share a common goal for peace and security for every Ghanaian citizen regardless of their “race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender” [Article 12 (2) of the 1992 Constitution]. We vehemently oppose the proposed bill for the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values. The bill is unconstitutional, and contains far-reaching consequences for the freedoms of all Ghanaians and people who live in, or visit Ghana. The bill is widely impractical, and an overreach that will affect almost every aspect of the private lives of all Ghanaians and people living within Ghana, irrespective of their sexual orientations or beliefs.

Unconstitutional Nature of the Proposed Bill

In proposing this bill, Parliament seeks to criminalize and deny the existence and basic human rights of persons who are otherwise intrinsically protected by the constitutional safeguards enshrined in our Constitution; namely, in Chapter 5:

- (i) Article 12 which guarantees the protection of the fundamental human rights of every person in Ghana;
- (ii) Article 13 which guarantees the right to life of all persons;
- (iii) Article 14 which acknowledges the right to personal liberty;
- (iv) Article 15 which provides that the dignity of all persons shall be inviolable;
- (v) Article 19 which notes that any person charged with a criminal offence shall be given a fair hearing within a reasonable time by a court;
- (vi) Article 21 which highlights the freedom of association; and
- (vii) Article 33 which guarantees protection of rights by the courts.

This bill violates all these constitutionally-given freedoms and seeks to take these rights away from Ghanaians. By doing so, it suggests that LGBT+ people as well as allies and advocates are to be stripped of their personhoods under the 1992 Constitution.

Clause 1 - This targets a long list of persons, including allies, as well as those with genetic differences from birth, such as people who are intersex. The clause criminalizes people solely for their identities, even before committing any actions which may allegedly be considered as improper.

Clause 12 – This targets pro-LGBT+ advocacy, the criminalization of which will infringe on the general fundamental freedoms of Ghanaians. Article 21 of the Ghanaian Constitution states that “All persons shall have the right to-

- a. Freedom of speech and expression, which shall include freedom of the press and other media;
- b. Freedom of thought, conscience and belief, which shall include academic freedom;
- c. Freedom to practice and religion and to manifest such practice;
- d. Freedom of assembly including freedom to take part in processions and demonstrations;”

All the above rights will be infringed upon and violated by criminalizing people’s ability to advocate for any form of human rights and will introduce a slippery slope for the protection of other basic human rights.

Concern for Safety and Wellbeing of Ghanaians

Many aspects of this bill can be misconstrued, leading to unsafe environments for numerous Ghanaians and people living in Ghana.

Clause 5 - The bill encourages people to report suspected and alleged LGBT+ persons, while claiming to be concerned with the safety of LGBT+ persons. First and foremost, this section holds bystanders accountable for reporting alleged LGBT+ persons, and “assist[ing] the police in the investigation and prosecution of the matter.” This raises many questions on the ways in which the bill can

- (a) Inadvertently and maliciously be used regardless of circumstance;
- (b) Extend the average citizen undue capacity in the face of unverifiable events;
- (c) Threaten the goals of impartiality of investigations and law enforcement.

Clause 9 - This section targets landlords and homeowners, which not only puts them at unfair risk of imprisonment, but opens up the possibility for extreme, inordinate renter and tenant discrimination.

Clause 22 - Should this bill pass, it will breed and encourage already existing intolerance and homophobia. Violent mob attacks against members of the LGBT+ community are already far too

common in Ghana. There have been many reports of physical and violent homophobic attacks and vigilante movements against LGBT+ people, whether suspected or allegedly self-identified (Human Rights Watch, 2018). The fact is, statements and policies such as the one proposed in this bill, championed by public officials and leaders, have a powerful impact, and can embolden aggression and lead to increased acts of violence towards marginalized and criminalized communities rather than their protection (we can turn the inflammatory rhetoric leading up to World War II, the Rwandan Genocide, cases of xenophobia in South Africa, etc. as leading examples)

Clause 20 - The Bill claims to protect LGBT+ persons, while presenting clause 20 and clause 23 which contradict these supposed protections by asking individuals to recant their LGBT+ status and undergo “approved medical treatment”, also known as conversion therapy, at their own cost. There is no evidence that gender and sexuality conversion works, or that sexual orientation or sexual attraction can be treated, altered or ‘fixed’. Infact, many medical and human rights bodies have proven that conversion therapy programs are extremely harmful an abusive, both physiologically and psychologically (Ogunbajo et al. 2021; Ohema Birago Oware, 2021).

Ambiguous, Impractical and Open to Abuse

The bill gives parliament the power to “actualize the intentions of the framers of the constitution by providing a legal framework for the promotion of the values that define our nationhood” (page 6). Except for a broad definition of family, there is no indication as to what legal framework will be used to develop these laws, and under what basis these laws will be put in place. Ghanaians are allowed freedom of religion and religious expression, therefore these laws cannot be implemented based on Christian or Muslim values, and once again, a harmful causal sequence may arise from bestowing parliamentarians with the authority to define morality.

Certain clauses in this bill are similarly impractical, namely:

Clause 12 and 13 - This clause asks for the prohibition of propaganda, promotion, and advocacy of activities prohibited under this act, by calling for the imprisonment of persons who disseminate any material promoting LGBT+ rights through media and technological platforms, as well as calling for the imprisonment of the owner of the media or technological platform. As such, international streaming sites such as Netflix, and satellite television companies such as Multichoice, which broadcast LGBT+ based TV shows, as well as technological platforms such as Twitter that often support the wellbeing of LGBT+ communities and advocates for their rights as humans, must be banned throughout Ghana. In fact, the recent announcement by Twitter CEO, Jack Dorsey, declaring Ghana as the location for Twitter Africa Headquarters will consequently have to be rescinded, leading to reputational and financial repercussions, both of which Ghana relies on heavily.

Misdirection from real sexual crimes and the protection of real sexual victims

Despite the title of Bill, which purports to take an interest in a plurality of “Ghanaian values”, this bill seems to exclusively focus on an interest in criminalizing LGBT+ identities. Contrary to what one might expect from a bill that claims to take an interest in “protection of and support of children” (Clause 17), there is no mention of real, prevalent, and devastating actions and conditions that threaten the health wellbeing of children.

On September 1st, 2021, myjoyonline published data from the Ghana Health Service District Information Management System (DHIMS) on teenage pregnancy in Ghana. The report stated 555,575 teenage pregnancies were recorded in Ghana between 2016 and 2020. Of these, 542,131 were between the ages of 15 to 19 years and an alarming 13,444 girls were as young as 10 to 14 years old. However, and given the purported premise of this bill, there does not seem to be any section that expresses concern for or plans to address the widespread cases of predatory and abusive behaviour and crimes committed by “heterosexual” predators and criminals to truly protect children. A 2011 study carried out by Plan Ghana, as well as a 2013 study on Sexual Violence against Girls in School (Proulx, Martinez 2013) conducted by researchers from the University of Ottawa, both reported that children are being abused by teachers and caregivers, and yet, the bill which claims to promote the protection of children and proper sexual rights does not provide any sections to tackle these matters.

The violence of heterosexuality, from rape to adultery to sexual coercion in schools, religious institutions and places of work are not acknowledged as improper by the proponents of this bill. Therefore, at best, this bill is misdirected; at worst, it is a targeted attempt to control a marginalized community based on assumptions and insubstantial hearsay.

Claims of Anti-Ghanaian “Culture”

Clause 2 claims to outline what “Ghanaian family values” are and cites examples such as “the recognition of the nuclear and extended family as the basic unit for all Ghanaian ethnic communities” (Clause 2 (b) (i)), where in fact, this is colonial invention adopted in relatively recent times as compared to our rich history of following very diverse matrilineal and patrilineal family structures across ethnic groups. For a bill that seems to hinge on rejecting so-called Western imports and impositions, much of its argument rests on these very same imported ideas about family, marriage, gender, and sexuality.

For instance, Clause 2 (e) also alleges the “recognition in Ghanaian ethnic groups, of ‘gender’ as a social construct to only male and female humans each of whose gender is assigned at birth”. However, gender as it is described in this bill is, in fact, continues the erasure of a history of diverse gender constructions (e.g. the *agyale* traditions of the Nzema people); an erasure that was started by the promotion of Western-colonial categories (Adomako Ampofo et al., 2008).

Many esteemed African researchers have discussed constructions of gender across the continent and investigated the impact of colonialism on altering gender relations. African theorists have maintained that African societies have historically constructed gender in a wide range of manifestations, based on their distinct histories, socio-economic class, and culture (Mikell 1997; Bakare-Yusuf 2003; Arnfred 2011), whereas colonialism changed gender roles through colonial officials' imposition of European gender norms and patterns, including of exclusive heterosexuality, and male dominance/female subordination (Adomako Ampofo 2007; Arnfred 2011). In the last decade alone, there has been an explosion of African-centered research on non-heterosexual identities in Africa that demonstrates the plurality of sexualities present in Africa (Arnfred 2011; Helle-Valle 2004; Salo and Gqola 2006; Tamale 2011, 2013).

Conclusion

LGBT+ rights, i.e., the rights for people to be with who they love consensually and to live without fear from state-sanctioned discrimination, violence, and oppression, are a fundamental aspect of any democracy. The suppression and criminalisation of these rights, as presented in this bill are a huge threat to the lives, liberties, and wellbeing of people, as well as a signalling that Ghana is not as committed to human rights and protections as it claims to be.

The bill, which was proposed to champion the proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values, focuses mainly on criminalization of a specific group of people, and includes nothing about healthy sex education and social protections, such as what guardians, teachers, religious leaders and communities should educate the population on for their own safety. 34 out of 36 pages of the bill are devoted to criminalizing peoples' identities and behaviours, while only 2 pages reflect on how to "assist " people who are deemed themselves to "suffer" from personal identities that harm no one, not even themselves. The bill gives parliament and citizens inordinate capacity to speculate on one's identity, which, as well as the call to criminalize LGBT+ advocacy, may have far-reaching consequences on the rights and safety of all Ghanaians and people living in, or visiting Ghana.

It is our hope that you recognize that this Bill and the repercussions of it passing are undemocratic, dangerous and violates ideals of human rights. If Ghana is indeed a country that, as the proposed bill states, cherishes "societal ideals selflessness, communalism and good neighbourliness, hard work, discipline, truthfulness, compassion towards the weak and vulnerable...and every customary ideal that will help establish a free and just Ghanaian society and nation", we appeal to Parliament to seriously consider our aforementioned points and that this bill is rescinded in its entirety.

We hereby call on members of parliament to reject the proposed bill.

Signed on behalf of,
Concerned Citizens of Ghana in the Diaspora